

MEDICAL SCIENCES

WRINKLE BLANCHING AS AN INNOVATIVE APPROACH TO SKIN REJUVENATION

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Abstract

The article examines wrinkle blanching as a modern method of skin rejuvenation aimed at eliminating age-related changes and improving skin quality. Special attention is given to correcting wrinkles in delicate areas such as the eye area, forehead, and mouth zone. The main techniques are described, including botulinum toxin injections, the use of dermal fillers, laser procedures, and regenerative technologies. The necessity of a personalized treatment plan based on the patient's skin condition and individual needs is emphasized. The procedure not only eliminates wrinkles but also restores self-confidence, contributing to an overall improvement in quality of life.

Keywords: wrinkle blanching, skin rejuvenation, botulinum toxin, dermal fillers, aesthetic medicine, skin regeneration, wrinkle correction.

Introduction

Wrinkle blanching is one of the newest methods of modern aesthetic medicine. This technology helps restore youthful and refreshed skin. With age, the skin loses its firmness and elasticity, which leads to the appearance of wrinkles. These changes are most pronounced on the forehead, in the area of the eyes, and around the lips.

The skin around the eyes is the thinnest and most vulnerable area. It is often the first to show signs of wrinkles, giving the face a tired appearance. The forehead and the area between the eyebrows are also prone to the formation of deep lines, which become more pronounced with age. These lines are frequently associated with facial expressions and active mimicry. Wrinkles around the mouth, another common concern, manifest as vertical lines, often referred to as perioral or «barcode» wrinkles. They result from volume loss and changes in skin structure, making the face appear older.

Aesthetic medicine offers numerous solutions to address these changes. Wrinkle blanching has now turned out to be one of the most effective and popular

treatments. The use of personalized treatment combined with advanced technologies has made wrinkle blanching so successful. The results of wrinkle blanching improve the skin's appearance and enhance confidence among patients.

This paper aims to discuss the detailed mechanism of the wrinkle blanching technique, as well as its indications in wrinkle correction on various facial areas. Important steps involved in the procedure, its advantages, and its prospects in cosmetology are touched upon briefly.

Main part. Anatomical and physiological aspects of skin aging

The aging of skin is inevitable and accompanied by a series of changes in structure and functions. The epidermis becomes thinner with age, while the levels of collagen and elastin, responsible for firmness and elasticity, are sharply reduced [1]. As a result, the skin loses its ability to maintain its shape and resist external influences effectively. The deeper layers of the skin become dehydrated, and the level of hyaluronic acid decreases, promoting wrinkle formation (fig. 1).

Figure 1. Comparison of young and aged skin

Each area of the face has its special features that determine the nature and intensity of changes related to aging. The **skin around the eyes** is considered one of the most delicate areas of the face. Its thickness is only

about 0,5 mm, making it particularly susceptible to adverse changes. This area has almost no subcutaneous fat, which causes it to lose volume and elasticity more quickly. A certain contribution to the development of expression lines, known in common speech as «crow's

feet», is made by constant tension, for example, by orbicularis oculi. With age, this would deepen, and skin surface elasticity and smoothness decreased around the eyes.

Apart from age processes, ultraviolet radiation, insufficient moisture, and action of free radicals greatly affect the skin of this area [2]. This factor accelerates the degradation of collagen and elastin, amplifying the aging process. Additional stress for this area comes from improper skin care and mechanical impacts in the form of the habit of rubbing one's eyes. All these factors lead to the appearance not only of expression lines but also of structural wrinkles. Maintaining healthy and beautiful skin around the eyes requires treatments aimed at restoring hydration, stimulating collagen production, and protecting against aggressive external influences. Such approaches help preserve its firmness and prevent premature aging.

The forehead and glabellar area are zones with high levels of facial muscle activity. Every movement of facial muscles associated with emotional expressions leaves marks in the form of folds. In that sense, with increasing age, skin can no longer retract back into place following these contractions and, as such, expression lines will turn permanent. Horizontal forehead lines and vertical wrinkles at the space between the eyebrows often tend to give one the appearance of being fatigued or tense and thereby make a person appear much older than his/her real age.

An elevation in the activity of breakdown collagen and elastin synthesis with a thinning subcutaneous fat layer accelerates age-related morphological changes in the forehead and the glabellar area, yielding loss of skin elasticity and an inefficient mechanism of recovery. Continuously acting muscles like frontalis and corrugator supercillii develop deep folds, which deepen over a period of time as human age advances. Other contributing factors that involve environmental influences, such as ultraviolet radiation that degrades collagen fibers, along with stress, which boosts the frequency of facial muscle contractions, add to these alterations.

Effective methods for correcting these changes include techniques aimed at relaxing the muscles (botuli-

num toxin injections) and stimulating skin renewal (laser treatments or biorevitalization). These approaches can achieve noticeable rejuvenation and a more relaxed facial expression [3].

The **area around the mouth** is also significantly affected by age-related changes. Over time, the skin loses volume due to the reduction of fat tissue, weakening of supportive structures, and decreased collagen levels. This leads to the formation of perioral wrinkles – vertical lines surrounding the lips. These wrinkles are particularly prominent in individuals with active facial expressions or habits such as frequent lip pursing. They can give the face a stricter or even aged appearance, making the correction of this area especially important for overall facial rejuvenation [4].

External factors also include the influence of smoking, which decreases the oxygen level in tissues and accelerates the degradation of collagen, and ultraviolet exposure, leading to photoaging. Gradual loss of skin hydration and a reduction in hyaluronic acid synthesis worsen the process by making the wrinkles deeper. This is a delicate area to correct, not only to get rid of wrinkles but also to keep the natural proportions and dynamics of the lips. The method of restoring volume loss is through injections of fillers, while in microneedling, minor injuries to the skin are made to stimulate collagen production, improving skin texture for a fresher, more youthful look.

Changes in the skin, related to age, are the results of the combined influence of genetic predisposition, environmental factors, and lifestyle. Understanding anatomical and physiological features of each facial zone allows one to choose the most effective approaches to wrinkle correction and skin rejuvenation.

Modern techniques for wrinkle correction

Various technologies can effectively treat wrinkles caused by natural aging, reduced skin elasticity, and facial muscle movements. Each part of the face requires an individual approach, considering peculiar anatomic and physiologic features of it. Among the most valuable methods in the fight against wrinkles-one has the opportunity to restore a young and natural-looking appearance-are injections with botulinum toxin, dermal fillers, laser treatments, and peeling (table 1).

Table 1.

Modern techniques for wrinkle correction [5]

Facial area	Method	Mechanism of action	Results
Around the eyes	Botulinum toxin injections	Block nerve impulses to muscles, reducing their activity.	Reduction of mimic wrinkles («crow's feet»).
	Dermal fillers	Restore volume, smooth out deep folds, and support the skin.	Enhanced contours, correction of skin hollows.
	Laser therapy, peels	Stimulate collagen production and skin cell renewal.	Brighter skin, reduction of fine wrinkles.
Forehead and glabellar area	Botulinum toxin injections	Relax muscles, preventing the formation of deep folds.	Smoothing of horizontal and vertical wrinkles.
	Laser treatments	Improve skin texture, restore its density.	Reduced wrinkle appearance.
Around the mouth	Dermal fillers	Restore lost volume, fill perioral wrinkles.	Correction of folds, restoration of lip shape.
	Microneedling, chemical peels	Stimulate skin regeneration, improve texture.	Increased skin density, reduction of wrinkles.

The most modern methods of wrinkle correction allow for a huge spectrum of solution options for different types of age-related skin changes. The injections of botulinum toxin still remain the most effective way of getting rid of mimic wrinkles, first of all around one's eyes and forehead. Dermal fillers provide volume and help to correct deep folds, while laser technologies and chemical peels regenerate skin, improving its structure and looking better.

Each method has its own advantages, which can be enhanced through a comprehensive approach. An individualized correction strategy, tailored to the specific characteristics of the skin and the patient's preferences, ensures optimal and long-lasting results.

Wrinkle blanching as a comprehensive approach

Wrinkle blanching is a cosmetic procedure aimed at correcting fine and superficial wrinkles using injections of products containing hyaluronic acid or other biocompatible substances [6]. The main principle of this technique lies in the precise administration of the prod-

uct into the upper layers of the skin to provide hydration, smoothing, and stimulation of natural regeneration processes.

Superficial and minimal injections of hyaluronic acid-based products create a sort of micro-reservoir that guarantees the skin adequate hydration. This technique promotes skin quality, acting on hydration, stimulating collagen, and elastin synthesis, therefore making the skin more uniform and firm.

Wrinkle blanching is a notion that covers one single procedural concept, rather than the mere performance, based on the treatment approach of a patient in an individualized manner. In that respect, the essence of this approach lies not only in destroying obvious wrinkles but also, when possible, in increasing skin quality and elasticity or in restoring lost facial relief. The ultimate goal is not just rejuvenation but the achievement of a harmonious and natural appearance, which corresponds to the patient's age. Individualization of the treatment plan is a characteristic of wrinkle blanching (table 2).

Table 2.

Individualization of the wrinkle blanching plan [7, 8]

Stage	Description	Objective
Preliminary consultation	Collecting information about the skin condition, medical history, and lifestyle. Analyzing the patient's goals and expectations.	Determining indications, contraindications, and the approach to correction.
Skin condition diagnosis	Examination by a specialist using dermatoscopy or 3D-scanning to assess skin texture and density.	Identifying problem areas and determining the degree of wrinkles for accurate planning.
Defining target zones	Selecting areas requiring correction: eyes, forehead, around the mouth, neck, or décolletage.	Personalization based on the unique facial characteristics of the patient.
Product selection	Choosing the appropriate product (hyaluronic acid, combined products, collagen stimulators).	Considering the skin condition, patient's age, and desired outcome.
Injection technique development	Defining the depth and dosage of injections, choosing the method (microinjections, linear technique).	Maximizing effectiveness while minimizing side effects.
Post-procedure care	Recommendations for skin recovery: hydration, UV protection, avoiding aggressive treatments.	Supporting results and accelerating tissue regeneration.
Follow-up plan	Determining the number of sessions and intervals between them.	Ensuring long-lasting results and preventing the formation of new wrinkles.

Wrinkle blanching as a comprehensive approach demonstrates that modern aesthetic medicine focuses not on masking age-related changes but on deeply improving skin quality and the overall harmony of appearance. A personalized approach, combined with advanced techniques and technologies, enables the achievement of natural yet noticeable results, allowing patients to maintain their youth and beauty for many years.

Modern technologies and prospects in wrinkle correction

Modern technologies in wrinkle correction are continually evolving, offering patients increasingly effective and safe solutions. The primary focus is on improving injectable products and techniques, enabling natural and long-lasting results with minimal risks and discomfort. One of the most significant innovations in recent years is the development of modified hyaluronic

acid products. These provide prolonged effects due to their unique molecular structure, which enhances the product's flowability and adaptability to facial mimicry. This is particularly important for areas where active facial expressions can lead to the rapid breakdown of standard products.

In addition, biostimulators based on polylactic acid and polycaprolactone represent a major advancement in injection technologies. These substances not only fill wrinkles but also stimulate the production of natural collagen, restoring skin firmness and density. Combined formulations containing hyaluronic acid, vitamins, amino acids, and peptides have also become increasingly popular. They not only smooth wrinkles but also improve skin texture, restoring its healthy color and hydration.

Progress has also influenced injection techniques. Microinjections using ultra-thin needles are becoming

more common, minimizing tissue trauma and allowing treatment of even the most delicate areas, such as the eyes and lips. One of the popular techniques is local blanching, where the product is injected into the upper skin layers to smooth fine wrinkles and improve texture. The combination of injections with hardware methods, such as laser resurfacing or ultrasound therapy, is becoming a standard practice in modern cosmetology. This approach enhances the effect of procedures and allows simultaneous treatment of both superficial and deep skin layers.

The future of this field is tied to the adoption of personalized approaches, considering not only age and skin condition but also genetic factors, lifestyle, and individual responses to treatments. Technologies using artificial intelligence are already being employed to create optimal treatment plans and predict procedural outcomes. Another promising direction is the development of products with programmable release of active ingredients, which activate in response to specific triggers, such as muscle activity, allowing for precise targeting of problem areas.

Finally, cellular technologies, including the use of the patient's fibroblasts to restore skin structure, are opening new horizons in rejuvenation. These innovations enable tissue repair at the cellular level, providing a deeper and more lasting effect. All these developments make wrinkle correction safer, more precise, and individualized, allowing patients to achieve natural and harmonious results while preserving their beauty and youth. The information presented on these technologies is based on modern scientific research and practical experience in cosmetology, confirming its reliability.

Conclusion

Wrinkle blanching represents an innovative and effective approach in modern aesthetic medicine aimed at comprehensive skin rejuvenation and quality improvement. Contemporary methods, such as hyaluronic acid injections, biostimulators, and combined approaches using hardware technologies, achieve significant results in correcting age-related changes. The individualization of treatment plans and the use of advanced products ensure that the procedure is safe and tailored to each patient's needs. Comprehensive skin

treatment not only smooths wrinkles but also stimulates regenerative processes, enhancing firmness and restoring the skin's natural contours. Advances in technology and the adoption of personalized solutions provide long-lasting and natural results, making wrinkle blanching a promising direction in cosmetology that meets the growing demand for maintaining youth and beauty.

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